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APPROACHES TO STUDY THE BURDEN OF ILLNESS.

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Abstract

Ill health and, therefore, the need for healthcare can affect the allocation of existing resources of households. Healthcare demand depends on many factors, one of the most visible and important being healthcare costs. There are different approaches to study the economic burden of healthcare. The article discusses the different methodological approaches to study the burden of illness. The approaches include cost of illness approach (direct and indirect cost), human capital approach (Grossman 1972) and frictional cost approach (productivity loss), out-of-pocket expenditure on health and catastrophic expenditure. Some empirical evidence on the impact of the burden of healthcare on the households' economy is highlighted.

Keywords: *Burden of illness, direct and indirect cost, cost of illness approach, human capital approach, frictional cost approach, productivity loss.*

1. Introduction: Health and the derived demand for healthcare

Health is an important factor that determines an individual's economic and non-economic well-being (Desai, 1987; Strauss, 1986; Sahn and Alderman, 1988). It is also dictated by various factors, medical care being one such. Other factors include 'social class, work environment, employment status, income, housing conditions, education, diet, lifestyle, and so forth' (Andermann 2016). Williams (1990) discussed the 'association between socioeconomic and physical health status and the socioeconomic differential in morbidity'. Health seeking behaviors and its

outcome therefore can be linked to the individual's health conditions and economic factors such as employment and income

Illness can also affect labour market outcomes and social welfare. These effects are more complicated than mere shifts in 'productivity, changes in labour participation, or absenteeism' (DeLeire and Manning, 2003). Numerous theoretical models of 'nutrition-based efficiency wages' in development literature (Leibenstein, 1957) have increased our 'understanding and interest in the relationship between health and labour market outcomes in developing economies'. It has been argued that in poorer

economies where consumption levels are determined by income levels, individual physical wellbeing and productivity would depend positively on their nutrition and health status and thus on income.

According to Grossman's model of health production '*each individual is both a producer and a consumer of health*' (Grossman, 1972). Grossman's approach to demand for health, which is derived from human capital theory, shows how '*individuals invest in themselves, e.g., through training or education, to increase their productivity*' (Becker 1964, 1967, 1999, cited in Grossman, 2000). This theory proposes that '*an individual can be viewed as investing in human capital (health and education) to improve outcomes in both the market (work) and nonmarket (household) sectors*', i.e., "*individuals consume health care not because they value health per se, but because it improves their stock of health, which is used as a productive resource. Individuals therefore are not passive consumers of health but active producers of health through their investment in better health, using time and money* (Grossman, 1972)."

Individuals often attribute values to their health and wellbeing according to their productivity and economic capacity. This however, may not be a good determinant of the overall value of health i.e. both the intrinsic and extrinsic value. The value of good health should extend far beyond that. However, the value people attribute to health is difficult to measure because there is no direct observable market price. Individuals' valuation of their health can also be understood through the proportion of income they are willing to allocate on healthcare and wellbeing and also forego the productive time spent seeking healthcare.

Many factors both economic and sociocultural may determine demand for healthcare. The most visible determinant is the healthcare cost. According to Feldstein et.al (1988), '*the patient's demand for healthcare is affected by three broad factors: (i) the illness incidence and need for care; (ii) cultural and demographic characteristics such as age, education, marital status, number of persons in the family, employment status; and (iii) economic factors such as income, direct healthcare cost, indirect economic burden to the society (value of the patient's time)*'. Besides the three broad factors, '*other determinants of demand for healthcare also exist, such as quality of care, existence and type of insurance, taste, lifestyle, access to healthcare services—both in terms of cost and distance*'—and so forth. Anderson's model suggests that '*people's utilization of healthcare services is a function of their predisposition to use services, factors that enable or impede use, and their need for care*' (Anderson, 1995).

Done till here

In existing health economic literature, '*health is seen as one of the several commodities over which individuals have well-defined individual preferences*' (Jack, 1999; Phelps, 2017). Ill health and, therefore, the need for healthcare can affect the allocation of existing resources of the households. Thus, the demand for healthcare is at the cost of paying for care, and it depends on the ability and willingness to pay for healthcare, which in turn depends on the cost of healthcare and its various components. According to the World Bank (1998), '*the main economic costs associated with illness and, therefore, healthcare includes lost income from reduced labor supply and productivity, and medical care expenditures*' that may affect consumption patterns of families over periods of illness. The cost of healthcare can therefore have an impact on the resource allocation of the household, depending on

the nature and severity of the illness. It can also have substantial impact on household's ability to smoothen their consumption over a period. The opportunity cost of ill health is seen in terms of the impact of medical costs on expenditure patterns and the value of lost productive time (forgone income due to absenteeism) of patient and the caregiver. On the other hand, although costs are incurred, better health increases the number of days to be spent in earning income for the well-treated patients as well as their caregivers. The healthcare cost is therefore an important determinant of the demand for health and the demand for healthcare.

2. Methods

2.1. Methodological approaches to study the burden of illness.

The costs of healthcare and the resulting economic burden of illness for the households are studied using the following approaches:

2.1.1. Cost of Illness Approach

The economic impact or burdens of illness are generally studied using the 'cost of illness' (COI) approach. The approach is used to analyse the total cost incurred due to '*an illness from the perspective of the patient's, the healthcare provider or the society*'. According to Jefferson et al. (2000), "*the aim of COI studies is descriptive: to itemise, value, and sum the costs of a particular problem with the aim of giving an idea of its economic burden.*"

Prevalence method and incidence method are the two methods in which costs of illness are estimated. The prevalence-based estimates which incorporates the costs associated with all the affected patients in relation to a specific period are a cross-sectional view of costs associated with the illness. This method includes the total costs of an illness or disease within a stated time period, usually one year, regardless of the initial period of the occurrence of the disease. On the other hand, with the incidence-based cost-of-illness analysis '*the value of lifetime costs for new cases of the disease or illness*' (Rice, 1967) is computed. The incidence method only considers those patients who have fallen ill during the period. Discounting is done to reflect the present value of the costs of the illness incurred outside the period under consideration. To analyse the costs required for prevention incidence-based analyses are often used.

The following costs are generally examined under COI studies:

- Direct costs - incurred by the healthcare system, community and family in directly addressing the problem;
- Indirect costs - incurred by the individual, family, society, or by the employer and the macro-economy mainly through loss of productive days caused by the illness.

In COI studies, costs direct expenditure on healthcare and lost productivity and premature mortality related indirect costs are the two types of costs generally included in analysis. These foregone productivity costs are associated with the person who is unwell and to family members taking care of the ill, i.e., the patient and caregiver (McIntyre & Thiede 2003, Russell 2004). Various literatures have critically analysed the COI methodology. Consideration of the utility gain of reducing the illness and not just the costs of resources is seen as critical in the analysis. Non-comparison of alternative uses of resources may not adequately measure foregone or opportunity costs. The approach also does not

define availability of choices and cannot help directly in making them. Over-reliance on average rather than marginal costs, can lead to a systematic over-estimation of the size of the burden. Furthermore, more robust methods are needed for calculating indirect costs.

2.1.2. Human Capital Approach and Frictional Cost Approach

In health economic literature, economic assessment of cost of illness incorporate costs associated with productivity loss (Mullins et al., 2000). When assessing productivity losses, typically the human capital approach is used. This method estimates the 'value of potentially lost production (or the potentially lost income) as a consequence of disease'. This is 'an approach to valuing life in which productivity is based on market earnings and an imputed value for housekeeping services.' In the human capital approach, a person is seen as producing a stream of output that is valued at market earnings and the value of life is the discounted future earnings stream (Rice, 2000). Due to illness, there is a decline in time and effectiveness from work and various productive activities. Consequently, labour, a valuable factor of production is lost which might drive them out of labour force completely. Productivity losses are therefore estimated through changes in labour status and wages (Lopez-Bastida, 2009; Max et al., 1990). Examples of productivity losses include reported absent days from work and other activities due to the illness itself and for taking treatment.

Defining indirect costs as the 'value of production lost, more precisely as wealth lost, to society due to disease (and hence not as valuing lives per se)', the human capital method estimates the potential production lost, which may overestimate the actual production lost to a considerable extent (Koopmanschap et al, 1995).

The alternative to human capital approach is the frictional costs model which considers 'several economic circumstances that may reduce the estimated production losses substantially as compared with estimates based on the traditional human capital approach' (Koopmanschap and Van Ineveld, 1992). Cost as calculated by the friction method, is the value of displaced production (Jacob and Fassbender, 1998). Cost by this measure is less than the wage, because it assumes that some of the displaced production is made up. Here, production losses will be limited to the friction period, i.e. period needed to replace a sick worker or restore production. The structure of the labour market will determine the length of this friction period and the resulting indirect costs. For an estimate of the total indirect costs of a disease, two items are analysed: the costs per friction period and the frequency of friction periods (Koopmanschap and Van Ineveld, 1992)

2.1.3. Out-of-pocket expenditure (OOPE) on Health

According to the WHO (2005), out-of-pocket expenditure is defined as 'those payments made by patients at the point of receiving healthcare (both public and private)'. Out-of-pocket expenditure in existing literatures is measured to include 'all direct and indirect costs incurred by the individual and/or household in securing or maintaining their health' (Guthrie, 2004). It includes health service user fees, contributions to health insurances, consultation fees, treatment costs, costs of drugs (including traditional healers and medicines), additional costs in securing & maintaining health, e.g., nutritional supplements, transport costs, opportunity costs (loss of production costs), care and support costs as well as time costs. Further, 'inequalities in the financial burdens of the healthcare system are most likely to appear in out-of-pocket

expenditures' (WHO 2005).

Worldwide, out-of-pocket expenditure is measured in various ways. One way of estimating is by taking into account the health component in household income and expenditure surveys. Analysis of sub account of the say, HIV/AIDS section in national health account is another way of getting estimates of charges to HIV/AIDS patients from the providers. In studies in India, Bangladesh and Cape Town, financial diaries were used in which households were asked to maintain a 'detailed balance sheet of all income and expenditure and a monthly cash flow statement for duration of six months to two years' (Collins, 2005).

2.1.4. Catastrophic expenditure

Household expenditure on health is considered as catastrophic when it exceeds a critical minimum threshold which may be a proportion of some fixed household income or households' capacity to pay. According to Berki (1986), 'catastrophic OOP expenditure is one which constitutes large part of household budget and, thus, affects a household's ability to maintain a customary standard of living'. Wagstaff and van Doorslaer (2003) defined catastrophic OOP health expenditure as 'health expenditure that exceeds some fixed proportion of total household expenditure. Catastrophic payments capture only the extent to which households face large financial shocks due to health payments' (Murray et al., 2003). Xu et al. (2003) argues that catastrophic out-of-pocket expenditure should be defined in terms of a households' capacity to pay. According to the WHO (2005) definition, health expenditure is characterized as catastrophic when they 'are greater than 40% of a household's capacity-to-pay.

3. Some empirical evidences:

In India, the Out-of-pocket expenditures are estimated from a health and morbidity survey conducted by the National Sample Survey Organisation (NSSO) at a five-year interval. According to the National Health Policy (2015) out-of-pocket expenditure for health in India is 'one of the highest in the world and 55 million Indians fell into serious poverty-trap because of their health care spending during 2011-12'. 'In 2019-20 this share of Out-of-Pocket Expenditure (OOPE) in Total Health Expenditure (THE) declines to 47.1% from 62.6% in 2014-15' (NHA, 2020). Whereas maternal health services are expected to be provided freely at public health facilities in India, data from the National Family Health Surveys (NFHS) indicates that 'the OOPE per delivery in a public health facility at all-India level reduced slightly from Rs. 3,197 during NFHS-4 to Rs. 2,916 during NFHS-5'.

Due to minimal penetration of health insurance and reliance on out-of-pocket expenses, the high OOP expenditure affects the poorer quintiles adversely with the poor unable to access proper healthcare services or remain at high risk to catastrophic expenditure leading to poverty.

A study was done to estimate the burden of income loss due to ailment by Ghatak and Madheswaran (2011) using data from the 60th round of NSSO (Schedule No. 25.0) for the analysis. The information on loss of household income due to ailment computed as a percentage of total household expenditure both for inpatient and outpatient treatment across the NSS regions of India. On an average almost 22% of the annual household income is lost due to health reasons in India with a substantially high burden in the rural areas (more than 25%) compared to urban areas (12%). In both the rural and urban areas, the burden is highest among the poorest 20% of the population. In a study done using data from two longitudinal

Indian household survey by Shrinivas et.al. (2003) it was found that 'wage loss accounts for more than 80% of the total economic burden of illness among the poorest households, but only about 20% of the economic burden of illness among the most affluent'.

4. Conclusion

The incidence of the illness can inflict a major burden on patients and their families. Due to decreasing ability to earn income and rising expenditure on healthcare poor households plunge deeper into poverty. Occurrence of illness affect the lower income group in a different way due to their limited access to higher quality health services, which reinforces the positive impact that social inequalities (based on class, caste, race, gender, and nationality) have on the extent of prevalence of the illness. Ill health can contribute to impoverishment through the process of household assets depletion and income loss. Even when households manage to avert an illness-related financial shock, the strategies they adopt can have a cumulative and long-term impact. The extent to which impoverishments occur will depend on the coping strategies the households resort to. An understanding of the burden of illness on household will help in (i) identifying changes in levels of well-being, (ii) assessing the probability of impoverishment of the household, and (iii) assessing the performance of existing healthcare services, if any. There is much empirical evidence of the impact of illness on households' economic conditions through the substantial burden of medical expenses and the added loss of household income. Many households reported being pushed into poverty or forced deeper into poverty when faced with illness. Reliable estimates of direct and indirect costs of disease are indispensable for policy makers in setting priorities in health care.

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